

Conflict Management and Organisation Performance in Nigerian Tertiary Institution

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ABSTRACT

Background: Tertiary institutions in Nigeria operate in a turbulent environment that truncates their academic performance. Tertiary institutions are faced with numerous challenges in which conflict is essential to it. This prompts a need for appropriate strategies that would help them to build a healthy and uninterrupted working environment that would improve their performance. The question is now whether conflict management strategies adopted by the Federal Government of Nigeria as the employer (Management) to make a truce with the academic staff union of universities are jointly working to resolve the conflict between them that degenerated into industrial action. This study investigates how tertiary institutions in Nigerian strategically managed conflict to influence performance in their organisation.

Materials and Methods: It explored quantitative technique, the questionnaire was distributed to 357 respondents using a convenience sampling technique. Data collected were analysed with multiple regressions.

Results: The results statistically indicated that conflict management determinants (i.e. compromising and accommodation strategies) has a positive significant association with the organisation performance. The finding revealed that strategic management of conflict has a positive significant impact on the performance of organisation in Nigerian tertiary institutions.

Conclusion: The study implication showed that failure to utilise conflict management strategy effectively can impede organisational performance. The study suggested that the Federal Government of Nigeria need to make a critical change for the better strategies and focus on accommodation strategy, compromising strategies as well as alternative dispute resolution (ADR) to create a sense of belonging and avoid industrial action.

Keywords: *Accommodation Strategy; Compromising Strategy; Conflict Management; Performance, Tertiary institution.*

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INTRODUCTION

Nigerian institutions operate in a turbulent working environment nowadays where employees experience epileptic and interruptive work due to industrial action. Institutions are faced with many problems in which conflicts played a significant role, therefore institutions must search for appropriate strategies that would enhance their efficiency. Conflict management is very essential to the organizational performance (Omisore & Abiodun, 2014), numerous authors of conflict management asserted that conflict is an inherent component of the organisation; thus, conflict contributes to the performance of the organisation if managed constructively (Momanyi & Juma, 2016; Esquivel & Kleiner, 1997). Conflict management is of keen interest to directors and managers in the ministries or organisations because it facilitates harmony in the working environment.

Conflict management strategies have come to be one of the essential elements of scholarly literature on the context of conflict, and it mostly considered as major factors which employers/management depend on for resolving conflict. Managers and Directors must recognise how to effectively managed conflict to resolve dispute as well as to facilitate organisational performance (Henry, 2008), especially in the Nigerian universities. Authorities need to identify conflict management strategies that could influence harmonious relationships in a conducive working environment. In recent times, Nigerian universities workers have been experiencing several challenges including economic hardship due to issues of concern such as revitalization fund, stop using Integrated Personnel Payroll Information System (IPPIS) and put the University Transparency System (UTAS) into used for their workers and the payment of Earned Academic Allowance (Vanguard, 2022).

Approach to the Problem: The research study pointed out a lack of effective conflict management and inefficient strategies occurred between university workers (ASUU) and the employer (Nigerian government)(Wobodo, 2019). In recent times, the Nigerian government's failure to use appropriate conflict management strategies such as accommodating and compromising workers to avoid conflict has degenerated and led to industrial action. Specifically, in February 2022, The Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) that represents millions of universities employees all over Nigeria commenced industrial action (strike) started with warning strike which lasted for one-month over the conflict with the Nigerian Federal Government concerning rejection of UTAS platform for payment as an alternative to the Integrated Personnel and Payment Information System (IPPIS)(Agbakwuru, 2022).

In 2019, the Federal Government of Nigeria completed the arrangements to enrol the universities managed by Federal Government on the Integrated Personnel and Payroll Information System (IPPIS). The scheme aimed to foster probity, transparency and accountability in government expenditures and to achieve desired governance objectives in centralizing the payroll system. Contrarily, the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) argued that IPPIS introduced by the government into Nigeria's public Universities has hindered academic institutions' progress in the country(Pwanagba,

2021). Like every other sector in Nigeria, the education sector is bedevilled with collective disputes due to poor conflict management. The Federal government released some of the N30billion allowances to lecturers, while lecturers asked for a 23billion to be paid which would make a total of N53billion. The Minister of Education, Adamu Adamu stated that the Ministry of Finance has promised to conduct a forensic audit of the N30billion that was earlier released (Nwachuwu, Agbajileke, & Akinboade-Oriere, 2022), despite the initial payment of the allowance the total indefinite industrial strike continue. These have been serious issues of concern among students, academia, practitioners of human resources and the Federal Government. In spite efforts of government to reach an agreement with ASUU for a permanent solution, the issues remain unresolved due to inappropriate strategies adopted to manage the conflict.

Purpose of the Study: This study major objective is to investigate how strategies employed to manage conflict between the government (management) and the union representing university workers (ASUU) are jointly working, using accommodating and compromising strategies to resolve conflict.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Coser, (1957) defined conflict as a confrontation i.e. struggle or battle over power, values and resources or claims to scarce status, neutralise, eliminate or injure the rivals/opponents. Whilst organisation conflict is defined as a disagreement between groups or individual employees that are incompatible with one another, it happens to frustrate others' efforts and achieve separate objectives (Henry, 2008). Meanwhile, Roche & Teague (2012) defined collective conflict as a hostility between employers and employees about ordinary issues that commonly occur in the organisation. Collective conflict is a right contradiction which set off distinguish to influence a group of workers inside the organisation. Although, it is observed that collective conflict happens in numerous diverse environment therefore no definition is universally accepted for it. However, it is incontestable that the major cause of this conflict based on the fact that a group of workers standing collectively for a common goal. Therefore, collective conflict can be referred to as a disagreement over common issues such as discord over values, goals or interest which occurs between employer and a group of workers.

The concept of managing conflict in an organisation is a phenomenon which has been given enormous attention from academic literature and practitioners' perspectives (Prause & Mujtaba, 2015; Omisore & Abiodun, 2014). Practically, managing conflict has fundamentally become dimension of organizational behaviour. Because conflict is widely accepted as an essential segment of human resources management, consequently managing conflict effectively has been a major concern since it cannot be ignored. Managing conflict is necessary but it is becoming critical to managing conflict effectively. Conventionally conflict has been referred to as a destructive component. In the opposing view, Mohammed (2017) argued that conflict can provide some positive results if constructively managed. Some scholars such as Ajayi & Buhari, (2014), Iyiola & Rjoub (2020), and Giritli, Balci, & Sertyesilisik (2014) contested that conflict can be functional due to the output of intense debate that could ameliorate the quality of the

decision. Dineva, Breitsohl, Garrod, & Megicks, (2020) suggested that conflict in the organizational is permissible and found that there is a positive significant correlation between employee performance and effective management of the organisation.

Wobodo (2019) stated that functional conflict does not only benefit employee but also benefit organisation positively. It is agreed that effective management of conflict enhance commitment, leadership and teamwork success significantly (Roche, 2016). Contrarily, Gibbons (2007) contested that conflict is not beneficial to anyone, neither groups, individuals nor organisations. Conflict has negative influence on employee satisfaction and directly affect performance of the team. Therefore, managing conflict effectively is beneficial and very keen to the organisation and it can genuinely develop harmony between people as well as foster innovative, creativity and problem-solving (Dineva, Breitsohl, Garrod, & Megicks, 2020).

Several research studies had pointed out some critical strategies responsible for effective conflict management in the organisation i.e. accommodating, compromising, avoiding, competing and collaborating (Dundon, Wilkinson, Marchington, & Ackers, 2005). Although, research studies had emphasised the importance of accommodation and compromise strategies, but failed to establish the level of significance at which these strategies could ensure performance in the organisation (Gibbons, 2007; John & Devasheesh, 2010; Leat, 2014). This research study explores variables such as accommodating and compromising strategies to investigate the study objectives; therefore, accommodating and compromising strategies are used because of their importance to this research objectives.

Accommodating Strategy

Organisation can effectively managed conflict by putting one party's needs before another, and both parties must be ready to accept or give in to the needs of one another (Wobodo, 2019). Using accommodating strategy, involved parties needs to accept each other point of views. Momanyi & Juma, (2016) suggested that conflict could be managed effectively when involved parties seeks maintain peace by avoiding more pressure on concern issue and understand when to pick fight. Yusuf-Habeeb & Kazeem (2017) claimed that accommodating strategy is an important instrument which can be explored to resolve conflict, the results of their study show that conflict have a positive significant impact on the performance of organisation.

This was contested by Hussein, Salem Al-Mamary & Hassan, (2017), argued that accommodating strategy cannot assist an institution or organisation for more vital issues, as it does not have the potential to create a quality decision because it could lead to avoidance of several important issues. Conclusively, accommodating technique could effortlessly assist to settle disagreement before it degenerates into discord or conflict. And accommodating strategy can facilitate commitments since it give worker sense of freedom to express their grievance concerning the problems that their organisation is facing without retaliation. This approach is therefore an essential element which was explored as a determinant in this survey study.

Compromising Strategy

Momanyi & Juma (2016) posited that compromising strategy is adopted to identify soft ground which allowing or letting aggrieved parties absorb or concede parts of their needs and settle for a solution. A compromising approach is referred to as lose-lose strategy because it compels parties involved in the conflict to give and take as well as agree on certain conditions to settle most significant issues of concern (Dundon, Wilkinson, Marchington & Ackers, 2005). Contrarily, Kassim & Ibrahim (2014) contested that compromising technique cannot provide a long term solution to the conflict as no single conflicting parties would leave the negotiation or discussion table with total happiness. It is understood that a party may be unwilling to compromise in the future because they might feel as if they give up too much. For example, the Federal government of Nigeria felt like they are given up too much while ASUU on the other hand also felt the same. Subsequently, a compromising approach could help to settle the crisis faster, quickly and arrange for collaboration between the parties to which both conflicting parties would reach an agreement (Yusuf-Habeeb & Kazeem, 2017). However, a compromising approach can result in resentment if ineffectively used for conflict resolution; consequently, it could only be used sparingly. Compromising strategy can be explored as a determinant in this study due to its significance.

Organisation Performance

Hornby (2015) defined an organisation as a group of organised individuals with a specific objective/purpose, i.e. government ministry or business sector. Nene & Pillay, (2019) defined performance in the organisation as the actual results or outcomes of the company which is evaluated with the output planned. According to Almatrooshi, Sanjay, & Farouk, (2016), performance allows directors/managers to appraise, evaluate or assess an organisation whether its objectives were or not achieved; additionally growing as well as remunerate workers for a job well done. Managing performance is necessary to facilitate the objectives and goals of the organisation as well as align them with the desires/interests of the employee. Diamantidis & Chatzoglou (2019) affirmed that the objectives of the organisation and management of performance must be entwined with the morale and wellness of employees. In this perspective, organisation's success is dependent on conflict management effectiveness. It plays an essential role in ensuring a conducive business working atmosphere and also strengthening employee loyalty which could lead to performance in the organisation (Nene & Pillay, 2019).

Empirical reviews are conducted to come up with a deeper understanding as well as statistical support for the study's point of view. Melissa, Anna & Katie (2018) found that comprehensive training on how to manage conflict with productive communication are very important to systems at all levels. The results further indicate that training conflict management as well as productive communication are required for classroom conflict management effectiveness. Irene & Athanasios (2018) found that the transformational type of leadership has a positive correlation with non-constructive technique of conflict management, consequently transactional type of leadership has a negative correlation with non-constructive strategy of conflict management. Overall, the results of empirical study showed transformational type of leadership impact are comparatively stronger. Therefore, the results revealed that leadership plays significant

role in managing conflict, and this study is very relevant as the government failed to manage the conflict effectively.

Min, et al., (2020) investigates the association of supervisory behaviour, strategic management of conflict, and employee performance sustainability and survey mediating effect of strategic conflict management. The study collected information from SMEs manufacturer in Pakistan. PLS-SEM (structural equation modelling) was explored to assess model significance. The survey study found that supervisory behaviour has a positive and significant correlation with employee behaviour sustainability. Also, found that strategic conflict management has a positive significant impact on the supervisory behaviour as well as employee behaviour sustainability. It further established that strategic conflict management has a mediating role between supervisory behaviour and employee performance sustainability.

METHODOLOGY

This survey study used an explanatory design to investigate the cause-effect relationship due to its capacity to collect information that deals with the present issues. A quantitative method was explored to achieve objectives of the study because it is considered an appropriate design for a study of this nature that investigates the currently existing issues of conflict management and organisational performance in the Nigerian tertiary institution; thus, it helps to formulate a problem for research. The study surveyed lecturers working at the University of Ilorin (employees) and members of the academic staff union of universities (ASUU) who are currently working with a Federal university in Nigeria. Primary data was used through a structured questionnaire to collect information directly from the respondents without coercing or influencing their choices.

The study used convenience sampling techniques which allows the researcher to make use of available participants who are willing and volunteered to partake in the research process (Gay, Mills, & Airaisan, 2012). The questionnaire was distributed to 357 respondents, using 5 points Likert scale. Coefficients Cronbach's Alpha performed to check data reliability and the findings show .790 that is considered to be good enough to measure the scale under investigation and it is also acceptable. The study conducted One-way ANOVA to determine the discrepancy between the components. Therefore, multiple regression analysis was explored to establish the level of a significant association between determinants of conflict management and organisation performance. The p-value of 0.005 was considered to be statistically significant for the components.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

This study used multiple regression analysis to determine the level at which conflict management strategies (such as accommodating and compromising scales) can influence performance in the Nigerian tertiary institution. Preparatory analyses i.e. linearity, normality, homoscedasticity, and Multicollinearity were conducted in this study to ensure that assumptions of multiple regression were not violated.

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.555 ^a	.308	.304	.54428	1.495
a. Predictors: (Constant), CompromisingStrategy, AccommodatingStrategy					
b. Dependent Variable: OrganisationPerformance					

Source: Author Survey (2022).

The above table depicts the findings of multiple regression analysis with R Square value of 30.8%. This indicated that analysis of model fit (i.e. accommodating and compromising scales) described about 30.8% of the variance in the organisation performance of Nigerian tertiary institutions. The study revealed that strategies of conflict management dimensions such as accommodating and compromising can predict the performance of Nigerian tertiary institutions. However, Durbin-Watson Statistic shows 1.495 coefficients that revealed the absence of serial correlation regarding a model error, thus the issues related to spurious regressions are eliminated.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	46.620	2	23.310	78.686	.000 ^b
	Residual	104.869	354	.296		
	Total	151.489	356			
a. Dependent Variable: OrganizationPerformance						
b. Predictors: (Constant), CompromisingStrategy, AccommodatingStrategy						

Source: Author Survey (2022).

The ANOVA was carried out to check if the means views of respondents are significantly different from each other. The findings of ANOVA for this study show F-test with 78.686, significant at level of 1 per cent [$p < .000$]. It showed that the models explored for this study was well specified as it properly checked the impact of strategic conflict management dimensions (i.e. accommodating and compromising scales) by comparing the means from various respondents such as members of the academic staff union of universities (ASUU) and other workers from university.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.865	.191		9.752	.000
	AccommodatingStrategy	.350	.058	.354	5.994	.000
	CompromisingStrategy	.225	.053	.253	4.281	.000
a. Dependent Variable: OrganizationPerformance						

Source: Author Survey (2022).

Table above revealed the coefficients of multiple regression findings of accommodating strategy which has a positive significant impact on the performance of

tertiary institutions in Nigeria. The accommodating strategy indicated β coefficients with .354, a t-value with 5.994 at sig of .000. This is statistically significant regarding the Beta coefficient, t-value, and p-value. Thus, a unit increased of accommodating strategy score bring about a unit increase of .354 and 5.994 in the performance of tertiary institution in Nigeria. By implication, this implies that accommodating strategy as a determinant of conflict management can facilitate conducive, harmonious and uninterrupted academic sessions which in turn could lead to a performance in Nigerian tertiary institutions.

The multiple regression coefficients revealed the level of compromising strategy strength as a dimension of strategic conflict management in the performance of the tertiary institution in Nigeria. Compromising strategy showed positive and significant influence with a β coefficient of .253, t-value of 4.281 at p-value [sig = .000]. The results implies that an increased unit of compromising strategy score could bring about increase unit with .253 and 4.281 in the performance of tertiary institution score. This suggested that compromising strategy have potential to determine performance in Nigerian tertiary institutions through uninterrupted academic programmes.

Discussion of findings

This study investigate the effect of strategic conflict management between the Government as an employer (Management) and the academic staff union of universities (ASUU) at Nigerian Federal University. This study objective planned to be achieved by exploring the issues of collective conflict that occurred between the Federal government (Management) and ASUU (employees) that had bedevilled Nigerian tertiary institutions. Specifically, conflict management strategies adopted by the Federal government (Management) i.e. accommodation strategy and compromising strategy to conflict resolution had degenerated into industrial action as well as increasing performance in the institution. The findings of multiple regression coefficients indicated that all determinants of conflict management strategies examined have a positive significant impact on developing uninterrupted academic sessions which could lead to a performance in a tertiary institution.

The study revealed that an accommodation strategy could positively create a harmonious working environment that can bring about employee performance in the tertiary institutions. The study established that accommodation strategy is an essential component that can help to resolve conflict and strategically it could increase performance in the institution. From every indication, it seems the Federal government as an employer adopted this strategy to resolve conflict with the academic staff union of universities (ASUU) but could not yield a positive result, as many respondents prove that the Minister of Labour and his counterpart from education which represented Federal government on the negotiation table show unconcern about the plight of ASUU specifically regarding UTAS. Although the results of study were supported by findings of an empirical research that Iyiola&Rjoub(2020) carried out on management of conflict to develop association quality among contractors and owners of Construction Company, it also investigate the role of trust as a mediating factor. The results indicated that climate of conflict management has a significant impact on trust and relationship quality. It also revealed that trust has a partial mediating association between climate of conflict

management and relationship quality. The study highlighted the importance of managing conflict in the organisation.

This study also established that a compromising strategy has a positive significant impact on conflict resolution adopted by the Federal government in Nigeria. Although the view of some respondents showed otherwise; thus, the findings of multiple regression coefficients revealed that large per cent of respondents agreed on the compromising strategy adopted by the Federal government as a conflict resolution method was used effectively. Consequently, these findings supported by the research that Yusuf-Habeeb&Kazeem (2017) conducted previously. The study established that a compromising approach can settle conflict as fast and quick as possible, also it has potential to set collaboration stage for conflicting parties to reach agreement. However, adopting a compromising strategy to settle dispute in Nigerian tertiary institutions is not just resolving industrial action between the Federal Government as an employer (Management) and the academic staff union of universities as an employee (ASUU) but also solidified employment relationship in the academic working environment that could improve performance.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Having examined the findings of this survey study, it is proven that Federal government and the academic staff union of universities (ASUU) keep a good relationship that based on mutual respect. Despite persistence of conflict between them, they both maintain cordial relationship. Although, in the workplace conflict is inherent, perhaps the present conflict that deteriorate to industrial action has been a long-term conflict. The Federal Government of Nigeria must make a crucial improvement on the effectiveness of conflict management strategies which was adopted presently for the resolution of dispute with ASUU.

It is suggested that Federal Government as employer (management) need to focus on dimension such as accommodation strategy. The Government need to reasons along with workers of universities, gives in to their needs and interest to create a healthy and conducive workplace. In a circumstance where the workers demand goes beyond government budget, for instance in a situation where the government found the issues of removing university workers from the IPPIS scheme difficult, the government need to dialogue with them, evaluating and finding a way to integrate UTAS designed by them if possible. Based on this study findings, it is suggested that Federal Government (Employer) should be engaged and communicate with the academic staff union of universities (ASUU) to inform university employees about the benefit of their policy and why it is necessary to include them, or listening to their point of view, this would have created a sense of belonging among the union representing employees.

It is suggested that the Federal government should allow direct participation of the employee in a decision that affects them, especially on the issues concerning IPPIS and UTAS to gain their trust and loyalty. The federal government must compromise on the issues of IPPIS by allowing UTAS which accommodates their allowances and other demand as an alternative to IPPIS which covers a few of their demands. The issues of

allowance should not be taken with levity by the Federal Government (Management) as well as regular payment of the employee salary. Therefore government should also adopt alternative dispute resolution (ADR) as a strategy to avoid conflict degenerating into industrial action that always disrupts academic sessions that affect students as well as the performance of university workers. Other approach such as alternative dispute resolution (ADR) including mediation, conciliation and arbitration could have helped to settle the conflict amicably and help to avoid industrial action.

Conclusion

This study used a quantitative approach to evaluate the aggregate predictors of conflict management strategies which can facilitate performance in a tertiary institution. The study used a survey method to evaluate conflict management strategies predictors i.e. accommodation strategy and compromising strategy to ensure a healthy working environment that can ensure performance of the institution. Conclusively, the established that conflict management strategy could significantly and positively influence performance in the tertiary institution by creating conducive and a healthy working environment. Based on this study findings, it is confirmed that conflict management strategy contributed exceptionally to the performance of Nigerian tertiary institution by ensuring academic session uninterrupted. It is also concluded that conflict management strategy effectiveness can enhance workers commitment which could result in the institution's performance.

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